

Congestion Management of Packets Based Network in GSM Using Shadow and Paris Metro Pricing Scheme

Olawale S. Yekini ✉, Godwin O. Igbinsosa ✉, Gerard N. Obiora ✉ ,
Owomano N. Imarhiagbe ✉, Abayomi A. Oke ✉, Iyabo R. Ebosele ✉
Department of Electrical/Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering, College of
Engineering, Bells University of Technology, Ota, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Wireless communications have experienced geometric growth. Global System for Mobile communication operators have taken several measures to expand their network facilities as a result of increase in demand but have not been able to combat congestion problem in packet network. One of the main issues that modern Internet users face is network congestion. A dynamic pricing system called Paris metro pricing (PMP) addresses packet network congestion, like that found in the internet. It is employed to divide a network into multiple logical networks, each of which would do its best to treat every packet equally. The only difference between the various networks would be the cost of using them. On the other hand, the concept of shadow price involves the use of marks. Marks are issued when network is congested. A mark represents a set amount that the user must pay to send packets. In this study, software using flutter framework application was built to simulate a prototype typical base station. Presentation and analysis of the obtained experimental results of the two dynamic pricing schemes shows that Shadow pricing is more efficient in managing congestion than PMP. Furthermore, the combined effect of both pricing schemes manages congestion effectively and generated more revenue.

Keywords: Congestion, Packets, Shadow pricing, Paris metro pricing, Flutter.

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INTRODUCTION

The phrase "Global System for Mobile" (GSM) communication is widely used by all and sundry. This is because communication is so essential to human existence and because everyone may utilize the GSM network, regardless of their social and financial status [1]. All network resources, including router processing time and link throughput, have limits, which is the core issue. If precautions are not taken, users may easily overwhelm (congest) specific networking resources, rendering the network inoperable. This observation, along with actual experience, indicates that there is significant congestion in GSM network operations, which has negatively impacted users in general. Most communication networks have a feature called congestion control. Almost all of these networks inherently become less effective in overload scenarios, and they frequently transport less traffic overall than they would in lower stress scenarios. In order to reduce congestion, some traffic that

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would typically have been transported must be delayed or refused to be carried [2]. A number of strategies, such as borrowing of channel, splitting of cell, sectoring of cells, creating micro cells, dynamic channel allocation and implementing handover methods, have been tried to prevent and control congestion in mobile networks [3].

This study's goal is to use Shadow and Paris metro pricing schemes in managing congestion of packet network. The PMP divides a network into multiple networks that make sense independently. Each would be limited to a set percentage of the network's total capacity. Every network would transport packets with equal treatment across all protocols. Clients would select the network on which to send their packets and make the appropriate payment [4]. Shadow pricing on the other hand, provide network users with enough information to enable them to decide for themselves whether or not to transmit packets. When resources are generated, this is accomplished by allocating marks on packets that correspond to a set price. All pricing mechanisms affects customers demand which invariably modify traffic loads.

LITERATURE SURVEY

In [5], marking packets when resources are overloaded and charging a fixed price for marked received by packets ensures efficient use of the network. Though, the authors did not explicitly consider the market structure within which the network operates. For [6], end to end window technique was utilized in enhancing congestion control of network operators within selected areas, The authors opine that operators need to formulate congestion control mechanism. The implementation of an ideal pricing approach that is closely matched by a well-chosen static price that is independent of immediate congestion was carried out by [7]. In doing so, they considered a single shared resource. Only Paris metro pricing was utilized by [4] in managing traffic in a packet network but quality of service cannot be guaranteed. In the study carried out by [8], a dynamic load balancing technique coupled with call admission control was used to manage call traffic on homogenous networks only. Dynamic pricing when used effectively can regulate demand and increase revenue according to [9]. It was discovered that a lot of available channels are being underutilized from the study carried out by [10]. Thus, congestion can be controlled in affected cells by ensuring the effective utilization of the underutilized channels. Traffic-class prioritization algorithm was used by [11] during high demand periods for managing traffic in networks. Just like [4], same author in [12] utilized the exact price scheme. The goal of the study executed utilized price as a factor in managing traffic. This implied that expensive networks would attract less traffic due to fewer viewers. Within the context of a particular area in Abuja, Nigeria, Transmission Environment Monitory System (TEMS) software was utilized by [13] in evaluating the quality of service provided by different network operators. One network operator outperformed others within the framework of the kind of service rendered. Furthermore, summary of traffic relief methodologies in GSM based networks was executed by [14]. While [2,15-17] achieved congestion control using diverse approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

T3831 Base Transceiver Station (BTS) Setup

A true base station network is composed of intricate networks and demands a lot of processing power, making it almost impossible to imitate. In order to preserve the main features of a global representation, a smaller one is utilized. Each sector module contains 8 time slots. Each time slot contains 2 transmit radio equipment (TRE) or channels. Each transmit (Ts) carries only 2 data processing/packet network or 2 subscribers at a time but out of the 8 time slots, 2 slots are not in use; one slot is for signaling while one is for channel correction. Each sector module has capacity of 12 packet network at a time. Each BTS has maximum of 3 sectors, capacity of the BTS is $3 \times 12 = 36$ subscribers on a packet network at a time. To manage traffic in a base band unit (BBU), the frequency of the channel, data processing rate and the modulation value will need to be increased. The BBU reports to the radio network controller (RNC) through a link while RNC reports to the mobile service switching center (MSC) through a fiber interface using SS7 (signaling System 7) protocols. A BTS setup is depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1. T3831 BTS Setup

Base Station Simulation Application

The application was built using the Flutter framework. The application consists of a single page with multiple widgets to display information about the simulation. The first widget, which is the graph chart, shows the bandwidth utilized. The default maximum bandwidth is 2500Mbps; this can be adjusted by the operator using the control data section of the application. Implying that the bandwidth using the text field in the control data section can be increased or decreased. This was used to manage congestion of packets within a specified period. The control data section of the application displays current price indicator, which shows the current price per megabyte of the system. The default price when there is no congestion is \$4 per MB, but it changes per MB if the cells in the BTS are almost occupied. The Price per MB (\$) for the standard price and congested price per MB (\$) for when the system is experiencing congestion is fixed. There are two toggle switches; the first one where information about the simulation is displayed, is used to change the pricing algorithm and the second on the simulation data page is used to pause or continue the simulation. By default, the system uses shadow price, but the toggle switch can change it to Paris metro pricing. Figure 2 shows the simulation window interface.

Figure 2. Simulation Window Interface

From figure 2, the simulation data section displays useful information such as maximum bandwidth in megabytes, bandwidth utilized, total video data sent, revenue generated, and the number of packets in the wait queue. While on the other hand, the available channels section shows 36 box-like widgets arranged in a grid layout. The 36 box-like widgets represent the channel capacity of the BTS. The packets are processed using random probability sampling. This shows the channels being used in red and the available channels in green.

How the Pricing Algorithm Works

For Paris metro pricing, the 36 channels are divided logically into three with different prices. There is a standard price, Paris metro 2nd price and Paris metro 3rd price. The different prices take effect base on the pre-set percentage of occupied channels. The current price changes when preset maximum percentage channels are reached. All new packets received are put through a random Boolean generator to simulate getting a 'yes' or 'no' response from the user. If the randomly generated Boolean value is true, the user packet is added to a waiting queue and given a wait time in seconds, depending on the type of packet. The wait time determines how long the packet should remain in the queue before being terminated. For audio packets, the wait time is 3 seconds; for text packets, the wait time is 5 seconds; and for video packets, the wait time is 2 seconds. If there is available bandwidth before the wait time expires, the packet is moved to the packet manager queue, where it will be processed. The current price becomes the congested price, and all new packets received are put through a Boolean generator to simulate and a response is gotten from the user if ready to pay the new price. If the user agrees to pay the new price, the packets are processed and if not, the packets are dropped. The system creates packet every 50 milliseconds.

Paris Metro and Shadow Pricing Approach

The Paris metro pricing scheme was configured using three pricing schemes; the 1st being the standard price (\$4.00), 2nd price (\$8.00) and 3rd price (\$10.00). The percentage at which the different prices take effect was set at 30%/70%. The 30%/70% means that the 2nd price takes effect when 30% of the cells are occupied and the 3rd price takes effect when 70% of the cells are occupied. Subscribers are alerted when price changes and are given the option to either accept or reject. Once a price is accepted, packets are processed. If not, packets are dropped. The amount of video, audio and text sent at every 10minutes was recorded. The total packets sent and revenue generated is also noted same time. The total packets sent at every instant of 3hours were simulated.

In addition, shadow pricing notifies a user ahead as soon as there is congestion to decide when to submit packets. A packet receives marks when sent during congestion. A fixed price is assigned to every mark. There are two prices involve; standard price and shadow price. For this study, the shadow price was set at 30%. This implies that shadow price of \$8.00 takes effect when 30% of the cells are occupied.

RESULTS

Packets Processing Configuration

Three types of packets were considered: audio, text and video. The flutter application used a random Boolean generator to generate packets within the limits specified for processing. The packets are expressed in megabyte (MB) which can be varied to manage congestion on the network. The maximum bandwidth is set at 2000MB. This will allow proper capturing of relevant information needed. The following parameters were set for each generation and simulation of packets: minimum audio size, maximum audio size, minimum video size, maximum video size, minimum text size, maximum text size, Shadow price per MB, standard price per MB, Paris metro 2nd price per MB, Paris metro 3rd price per MB, and bandwidth (in MB).

Corresponding information of data sent, video data sent, audio data sent, text data sent, revenue will be displayed in the simulation data section during the processing of packets. PMP at 30%/70% is shown in table 1(a) for the first case of set data of the parameters considered.

Table 1(a). Paris Metro Pricing at 30%/70% - Case 1

Min. Audio	Max. Audio	Min. Text	Max. Text	Min. Video	Max. Video	Standard price	PMP 2 nd Price	PMP 3 rd Price	Band Width
10MB	20MB	1MB	5MB	50MB	100MB	\$4.0	\$8.0	\$10.0	2000MB

Note: Min. = minimum and Max. = maximum

Table 1(b) presents the corresponding information obtained for the first case of PMP set as in table 1(a).

Table 1(b). Experimental Result of Case 1 of PMP

Time (in minutes)	Video Sent (in Gigabyte)	Audio sent (in Gigabyte)	Text Sent (in Gigabyte)	Data Sent (in Megabyte)	Revenue (in Million)	Congestion
10	7.147	1.50	0.90Gb	9641	\$0.07	No
20	15.392	3.18	1.80Gb	21160	\$0.15	No
30	23.982	5.11	2.68Gb	32144	\$0.23	No
40	32.613	6.83	3.62Gb	43063	\$0.31	No
50	41.583	8.26	4.36Gb	54733	\$0.39	No
60	51.377	10.11	5.24Gb	66747	\$0.49	No
70	61.642	11.83	6.13Gb	79692	\$0.58	No
80	68.787	13.43	6.99Gb	89791	\$0.65	No
90	78.773	15.51	7.97Gb	102356	\$0.75	No
100	87.849	17.00	8.97Gb	113949	\$0.83	No
110	97.109	18.76	9.77Gb	125954	\$0.92	No
120	105.679	20.37	10.66Gb	137363	\$1.00	No
130	115.635	21.94	11.60Gb	149463	\$1.09	No
140	125.758	23.70	12.35Gb	162128	\$1.17	No
150	132.894	25.50	13.30Gb	172513	\$1.25	No
160	142.475	27.52	14.24Gb	184753	\$1.35	No
170	149.352	28.96	15.10Gb	193977	\$1.41	No
180	159.339	30.65	16.03Gb	206162	\$1.50	No

PMP at 30%/70% is shown in table 2(a) for the second case of set data of the parameters considered.

Table 2(a). Paris Metro Pricing at 30%/70% - Case 2

Min. Audio	Max. Audio	Min. Text	Max. Text	Min. Video	Max. Video	Standard price	PMP 2 nd Price	PMP 3 rd Price	Band Width
20MB	30MB	5MB	10MB	100MB	150MB	\$4.0	\$8.0	\$10.0	2000MB

Table 2(b) presents the corresponding information obtained for the second case of PMP set as in table 2(a).

Table 2(b). Experimental Result of Case 2 of PMP

Time (in minutes)	Video Sent (in Gigabyte)	Audio sent (in Gigabyte)	Text Sent (in Gigabyte)	Data Sent (in Megabyte)	Revenue (in Million)	Congestion
10	16.287	3.18	2.12	23129	\$0.16	No
20	30.685	5.68	4.71	42199	\$0.30	No
30	45.103	8.63	7.06	61089	\$0.44	No
40	58.493	12.02	9.36	81388	\$0.58	No
50	74.277	15.32	11.80	101432	\$0.74	No
60	87.892	18.64	14.36	120995	\$0.89	No
70	101.649	21.61	16.76	140216	\$1.02	No
80	114.881	24.20	19.24	159397	\$1.06	No

90	128.52	26.88	21.68	177594	\$1.29	No
100	142.515	29.57	24.45	197358	\$1.43	No
110	159.383	32.23	26.99	218912	\$1.60	No
120	173.787	35.14	29.61	238881	\$1.75	No
130	188.369	38.07	32.01	258979	\$1.89	No
140	203.714	41.32	34.28	280033	\$2.04	No
150	217.757	44.32	36.89	299901	\$2.18	No
160	231.206	47.23	39.35	318139	\$2.32	No
170	245.235	50.25	41.73	337925	\$2.47	No
180	260.934	53.05	44.06	359055	\$2.67	No

PMP at 30%/70% is shown in table 3(a) for the third case of set data of the parameters considered.

Table 3(a). Paris Metro Pricing at 30%/70% - Case 3

Min. Audio	Max. Audio	Min. Text	Max. Text	Min. Video	Max. Video	Standard price	PMP 2 nd Price	PMP 3 rd Price	Band Width
30MB	40MB	10MB	15MB	150MB	200MB	\$4.0	\$8.0	\$10.0	2000MB

Table 3(b) presents the corresponding information obtained for the third case of PMP set as in table 3(a).

Table 3(b). Experimental result of case 3 of PMP

Time (in minutes)	Video Sent (in Gigabyte)	Audio sent (in Gigabyte)	Text Sent (in Gigabyte)	Data Sent (in Megabyte)	Revenue (in Million)	Congestion
2	0.00	0.00	0.00	1995	\$0.00	Yes

Furthermore, three cases are presented with respect to shadow pricing at 30%. Table 4(a) shows the first case of set data of the parameters considered.

Table 4(a). Shadow Pricing at 30% - Case 1

Min. Audio	Max. Audio	Min. Text	Max. Text	Min. Video	Max. Video	Standard price	Shadow price	Band Width
10MB	20MB	1MB	5MB	50MB	100MB	\$4.0	\$8.0	2000MB

Table 4(b) presents the corresponding information obtained for the first case of shadow pricing set as in table 4(a).

Table 4(b). Experimental Result of Case 1 of Shadow Pricing

Time (in minutes)	Video Sent (in Gigabyte)	Audio sent (in Gigabyte)	Text Sent (in Gigabyte)	Data Sent (in Megabyte)	Revenue (in Million)	Congestion
10	9.043	1.49	0.89	112049	\$0.08	No
20	18.110	3.18	1.84	23239	\$0.16	No
30	26.064	4.77	2.74	34094	\$0.23	No
40	36.081	6.63	3.65	46499	\$0.31	No
50	43.816	8.09	4.49	56797	\$0.38	No
60	52.533	9.71	5.32	67787	\$0.46	No
70	61.182	11.24	6.17	79095	\$0.53	No
80	70.732	12.80	7.09	90858	\$0.61	No
90	79.895	14.23	7.99	102410	\$0.69	No
100	89.323	16.22	8.88	114553	\$0.78	No
110	98.436	18.12	9.84	126921	\$0.85	No

120	106.029	19.65	10.63	136774	\$0.93	No
130	116.303	21.45	11.47	149525	\$1.00	No
140	124.824	23.19	12.26	160291	\$1.28	No
150	133.985	24.87	13.11	172082	\$1.17	No
160	142.308	26.43	14.00	183036	\$1.24	No
170	151.314	28.11	14.91	194531	\$1.32	No
180	160.125	29.79	15.89	206571	\$1.38	No

Shadow pricing at 30% is shown in table 5(a) for the second case of set data of the parameters considered.

Table 5(a). Shadow pricing at 30% - case 2

Min. Audio	Max. Audio	Min. Text	Max. Text	Min. Video	Max. Video	Standard price	Shadow price	Band Width
20MB	30MB	5MB	10MB	100MB	150MB	\$4.0	\$8.0	2000MB

Table 5(b) presents the corresponding information obtained for the second case of shadow pricing set as in table 5(a).

Table 5(b). Experimental Result of Case 2 of Shadow Pricing

Time (in minutes)	Video Sent (in Gigabyte)	Audio sent (in Gigabyte)	Text Sent (in Gigabyte)	Data Sent (in Megabyte)	Revenue (in Million)	Congestion
10	13.243	2.76	2.25	19760	\$0.13	No
20	30.606	5.81	4.95	42576	\$0.28	No
30	45.865	8.07	7.24	61839	\$0.42	No
40	61.011	11.22	9.73	82023	\$0.56	No
50	74.313	13.82	12.24	100900	\$0.68	No
60	87.538	16.99	14.38	119558	\$0.81	No
70	102.065	20.04	17.40	140683	\$0.95	No
80	116.056	22.66	19.68	158995	\$1.08	No
90	130.035	25.52	22.07	178229	\$1.21	No
100	143.853	28.57	24.44	197927	\$1.34	No
110	158.614	31.49	27.07	217720	\$1.48	No
120	173.96	34.21	29.48	238465	\$1.62	No
130	188.262	36.97	32.18	258221	\$1.75	No
140	205.032	39.64	34.82	280236	\$1.90	No
150	222.273	42.97	37.20	302845	\$2.06	No
160	237.634	45.09	39.77	323583	\$2.20	No
170	251.914	48.67	42.37	343130	\$2.33	No
180	267.340	51.95	44.61	364954	\$2.48	No

Shadow pricing at 30% is shown in table 6(a) for the third case of set data of the parameters considered.

Table 6(a). Shadow Pricing at 30% - Case 3

Min. Audio	Max. Audio	Min. Text	Max. Text	Min. Video	Max. Video	Standard price	Shadow price	Band Width
30MB	40MB	10MB	15MB	150MB	200MB	\$4.0	\$8.0	2000MB

Table 6(b) presents the corresponding information obtained for the third case of shadow pricing set as in table 6(a).

Table 6(b). Experimental Result of Case 3 of Shadow Pricing

Time (in minutes)	Video Sent (in Gigabyte)	Audio sent (in Gigabyte)	Text Sent (in Gigabyte)	Data Sent (in Megabyte)	Revenue (in Million)	Congestion
10	14.567	2.83	2.41	20728	\$0.13	No
20	29.124	6.13	4.89	41400	\$0.26	No
30	43.263	9.19	7.06	59964	\$0.40	No
40	56.599	11.87	9.87	78615	\$0.53	No
50	70.896	14.74	12.28	97943	\$0.67	No
60	86.454	17.47	14.86	119117	\$0.81	No
70	99.025	20.14	17.39	137316	\$0.93	No
80	113.422	23.13	20.04	156608	\$1.06	No
90	129.074	25.79	22.43	177898	\$1.20	No
100	145.143	28.80	24.91	199541	\$1.35	No
110	156.45	31.90	27.39	217027	\$1.46	No
120	170.915	35.23	29.93	236821	\$1.60	No
130	185.273	38.81	32.70	256862	\$1.74	No
140	200.008	41.44	35.17	277869	\$1.87	No
150	215.925	44.84	37.56	299173	\$2.02	No
160	231.412	47.71	40.11	332130	\$2.17	No
170	245.828	51.19	42.60	339929	\$2.30	No
180	261.016	53.88	44.95	360053	\$2.49	No

DISCUSSION

For Paris metro pricing at 30%/70% of case one and two, the result obtained shows that as the size of packets increased, the total revenue generated also increases and no congestion was experienced. But for case three, congestion was observed within two minutes. Meanwhile, same set of packets data condition was implemented for the shadow pricing scheme; and from the results obtained, congestion was not seen for all three cases considered compared to the PMP scheme where congestion was observed from the third case just within two minutes. It is thus evident from the result that as the size of packets increases, the network will experience more congestion and imminent collapse using Paris metro pricing approach only. Therefore, to make up for this defect, dynamically utilizing both pricing schemes will help to manage congestion. Furthermore, the presence of congestion in a network will result in no revenue, and this will lead to losses for the network operator. So, if congestion persists and customers are not satisfied with the quality of service offered by a network operator, such customers may switch to other network providers that provide better services. Network congestion management, improve quality of service and generation of revenue can be attained with the hybrid utilization of both pricing schemes. The two-pricing strategy can be adopted in voice calls to manage incessant call drops experience by customers or subscribers.

CONCLUSION

In this study, a small representation of a real BTS was utilized (called T3831 BTS). The shadow pricing scheme makes up for the shortfall of the Paris metro pricing scheme. Thus, utilization of both schemes in packet based network will give better result and help manage congestion. It gives users the freedom to choose according to their needs and financial constraints. Both pricing schemes can be applied to the base station subsystem of a GSM network to manage congestion of packet based networks.

Simulation of a real base station network can be explored in future studies. Also, is the fact that the maximum bandwidth was 2500Mbps and the application was run for only three hours for every set of packets. These limitations as well constitutes further research.

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